

Spectrophotometric Study of the Complexation Reaction between Oxovanadium(IV) and Gallacetophenoneoxime

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GALLACETOPHENONEOXIME (2,3,4-trihydroxy gallacetophenoneoxime) was earlier employed as an analytical reagent for the gravimetric¹, amperometric² and spectrophotometric³ determination of various metal ions. Further study on the oxime shows that it forms a stable green complex with oxovanadium(IV) and a detailed spectrophotometric study is carried out. The solid complex is also isolated and its ir and esr spectra are studied.

Experimental

Gallacetophenoneoxime is prepared following literature procedure^{4,5} and a 0.1 M solution of oxime is prepared in 50% aqueous alcohol.

A stock solution of vanadium sulphate (BDH, England) is prepared in double distilled water and standardised against standard potassium permanganate solution.

The instruments used for optical and pH measurements are the same as those reported in the earlier communication⁶.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of the green complex of oxovanadium(IV)-gallacetophenoneoximate shows λ_{max} at 395 nm and broad shoulder at 560-570 nm (Fig. 1). The reagent has a little absorbance at this wavelength.

The colour of the complex was stable within the pH range of 3.0-5.0 both in the buffered and unbuffered solutions. Hence all the measurements were carried at pH 4.5 using phthalate buffer. The absorbance of the complex remains constant for more than 24 hr. The system obeys Beer's law up to a concentration of 2.5 ppm. The optimum concentration range as per Ringbom plot⁷ is 0.15-2.0 ppm. The molar absorptivity of the complex was $\epsilon = 1.51 \times 10^4$ lit. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and the photometric sensitivity⁸ was 0.0033 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The stoichiometry of the complex in solution is established as 1:2 by Job's method of continuous variation method and mole ratio methods. The stability constant calculated from Job's curve is found to be 1.6×10^6 .

Structure of the complex: The solid complex of oxovanadium-oxime was prepared by mixing

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of V(IV)-Oxime complex at pH: 4.5
(A) V(IV)-Oxime complex vs reagent blank
[V(IV)] = 5×10^{-5} M.
(B) Reagent blank vs solvent mixture
[Oxime] = 1×10^{-3} M.

stoichiometric proportions of ligand and metal in methanol, the pH was adjusted to 5 and refluxed on a water bath for half an hour. The resulting solution was concentrated and the green complex was separated out by treatment with inert solvent. The separated complex was vacuum dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. The complex is insoluble in non-polar solvents but soluble in methanol, MIBK, nitrobenzene etc.

The complex was analysed for its nitrogen and vanadium contents to determine its composition. The composition of the complex corresponds to the formula $\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{N})_2$ in which vanadium to ligand ratio is 1:2. Found: N, 6.37; V, 11.61. Calcd.: N, 6.50; V, 11.82%.

The molecular weight of the complex has been determined in nitrobenzene by cryoscopic method and shows the compound to be monomeric.

A comparison of ir spectra of the complex with that of the reagent shows that the hydroxyl group frequency gets shifted from 3300 cm^{-1} in the complex. This shift in frequency is indicative of chelation to the metal. Similarly, the shifting of strong band at 1620 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$) in the reagent to downfield 1565 cm^{-1} in the complex is due to coordination through nitrogen of the oxime group.

The peak due to $\nu\text{N}-\text{O}$ observed at 960 cm^{-1} in free ligand is shifted to 950 cm^{-1} in the complex. The bands appearing at 990 cm^{-1} and 1125 cm^{-1} are due to $\text{V}=\text{O}$ stretching mode. Similar observations were reported in the study of oxovanadium complexes^{7,8,9}.

The esr spectrum of the complex was recorded at room temperature. The g_0 and g_1 values calculated from graph are 2.08 and 2.03 respectively.

Kivelson and Neiman¹⁰ have shown that g_{II} is a moderately sensitive function for indicating covalency. Normally g_{II} is 2.3 or more for ionic environment and it is less than 2.3 for covalent environments. The present result shows that g_{II} is less than 2.3, suggesting that the complex is covalent in nature. Similar observations were also made with other ($S = \frac{1}{2}$) copper complexes¹¹.

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Hydrogen Ion Equilibria on *p*-Toluenesulphonylated Casein

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THE role of surface active agents in affecting changes in the biological systems is well recognised. They exert disruptive influence on the cell membrane¹, act as tuberculostatic agents², increase the concentration of sulphones on the cell surface, form complexes with proteins^{3,4} (albumin-sodium alkyl sulphate complexes). Sulphonylated proteins are also known for their physiological activity.

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In view of the above it was envisaged that modified proteins can serve as good models to understand the nature of such reactions. As a first step, investigation to determine their reaction sites is necessary. It was best achieved by carrying out hydrogen ion equilibria studies by various workers particularly Linderstrom⁵, Tanford⁶, Cannon⁷, Malik⁸⁻¹⁰.

This paper gives the result of hydrogen equilibria studies on *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein along with those on the binding of H⁺ and OH⁻ ions to whole casein reported earlier¹¹.

Experimental

Solution : *p*-Toluene sulphonylated casein used was prepared by the method of Gurin and Clarke¹². Sulphur content was found to be 1.945%. Solution of *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein was prepared at pH 6.5, using KOH. Its concentration was determined by drying a known aliquot at 105°. The correction for potassium ions was applied to get the absolute weight of protein. Carbonate free hydroxide was prepared as recommended by Kolthoff¹³. Potassium chloride, potassium hydrogen phthalate and sodium borate solutions were prepared by dissolving A. R. samples in doubly distilled water.

Apparatus and techniques : pH measurements were made on Beckmann model G pH meter, using glass electrodes. The pH meter was standardised by measuring the pH of 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate for the acid range and that of 0.01 M sodium borate for the alkali range. Purified nitrogen was passed slowly for about 10 min to ensure inert atmosphere.

Optical density was measured with Unicam spectrophotometer type SP 500, using a hydrogen lamp (slit width 0.1 mm and silica cells of 1 cm path).

Procedure : Varying amount of hydrochloric acid (0.0861 M), viz. 2.0, 1.6, 1.0, 0.8, 0.5, 0.3, 0.1 and 0.02 ml and 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.1, 1.2 and 1.5 ml of potassium hydroxide (0.0605 M) were taken in different pyrex tubes. Two such sets were prepared. In one set, protein was not added and total volume was made upto 10.0 ml by adding 1.5 ml of 1.0 M potassium chloride (to maintain constant ionic strength) and water. In the second set, the total volume was made 10 ml, by adding 4 ml of *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein solution (2.0%) and 1.5 ml of 1.0 M potassium chloride solution and water. The pH values of these solutions were then recorded at two different temperatures, viz., 20° and 30°. The results are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

Experiments were also performed to show the reversible nature of hydrogen ion equilibria of the protein both in the acidic and basic range¹⁴ of pH. The hydrogen ion titration curve was found to be reversible at moderate pH values.